

Greener Journal of Physical Sciences

ISSN: 2276-7851 ICV 2012: 5.88

A Preliminary Assessment of Phenol Contamination of Isebo River in South- western Nigeria

By

Omotayo Ayeni

Research Article

A Preliminary Assessment of Phenol Contamination of Isebo River in South-western Nigeria

Omotayo Ayeni

Department of Geography and Environmental Sciences, University of Hertfordshire, Hatfield, AL10 9AB, United Kingdom.

Email: omotayoayeni@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Wastewater samples were collected from the point of discharge at the various sites in an industrial area in Ibadan, Nigeria in order to determine and quantify the presence of phenols and their toxicity levels in the laboratory. Similarly, water samples were collected from Isebo River near the industrial area to determine the chemical status of the river with respect to phenolic contamination. Phenol was analysed using Skalar Auto-Analyser (SAA) while the physico-chemical parameters such as temperature, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS) and pH were determined using a Symphony SP80PC portable instrument. The results obtained showed higher concentrations of phenols in both water and wastewater samples. The phenol concentrations vary from one sample location to another while the range of values obtained for phenols in water samples is given as 0.05 – 2.11mg/L. The phenol concentration was greater than the permissible limit of 0.001mg/L recommended by World Health Organization (WHO) and Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ).

The coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.9816$ and 0.9991 of EC and TDS for both the wastewater and water samples shows a good positive correlation between the two parameters while temperature and pH varied anomalously with the recommended standards. This study reveals that the contaminant level of phenols in the water samples collected from the river could pose a huge health hazard to humans. Therefore, the polluting industries have the duty-of-care to manage the raw wastewater being discharged into the natural environment in order to preserve the aesthetic integrity of the water environment and to ensure public safety.

Keywords: Phenol, contamination, river Isebo, water, wastewater, WHO, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Control of water pollution has reached a remarkable level in developed and a number of developing countries. The prevention of pollution at source, applicable precautionary principle and the prior licensing of wastewater discharges by competent authorities have become key elements of successful policies for: monitoring, preventing, controlling and reducing inputs of potential hazardous substances, nutrients and other water pollutants from point sources into the natural environment.

The appearance of phenols as toxic organic acids in wastewater has attracted a global interest in the sphere of environmental management. Roux and Althoff (1980) report the presence of toxic organic compounds such as polyaromatic hydrocarbons, dioxin and phenols as important constituents of industrial wastewater. Thurman (1985) and Prasana (2001) reiterate that one of the worst toxic substances in our environment is the Persistent Organic Pollutant (POP). The river Isebo in Ibadan South-western part of Nigeria was assessed for its quality profile with respect to possible contamination by phenols emanating from the nearby industrial estate. The drainage system of the area is sub-dendritic to dendritic and is controlled by the topography.

Phenol is colourless with acicular crystals with characteristic sweet and acrid odour (Budaveri, 1996) and it is soluble in ethanol, water, chloroform, glycerol, carbon disulphate and alkalis. Phenol and phenolic substances are aromatic hydroxy compounds which are classified as monohydric (Bobranski, 1973). Akintade et al. (2012) report that phenol evaporates more slowly in ambient temperature than water. Phenol has a wide range of uses including the preparation of phenolic and epoxy resins, selective solvents for refining lubricating oils, salicylic acid, phenolphthalein, pentachlorophenol and other derivatives; in germicidal paints; as a laboratory reagent and in dyes; biocide and general disinfectant (Lewis, 1993). Occupational exposure levels to phenols have been documented (IARC, 1989) while the toxicity of these phenolic compounds stems from the generation of organic radicals and reactive oxygen species. More so, Phenols are released in the air and water as a result of their manufacture, their use in phenolic resins and organic synthesis (Wallace, 1996).

Several investigations have shown positive correlation between petroleum industrial pollutions of surface waters and the health of aquatic organisms (Mohammed et al., 2013). Some chemical substances have been reported to cause widespread health hazards in humans as a result of exposure through drinking water with excessive quantities or substances. However, this environmental risk has attracted global environmental

remediation interventions. The health objective of reducing the overall regime of health risks from all known sources of exposures to anthropogenic hazards has been proposed (Prusse, 2002; Ayeni, 2005; Prusse and Corvalan, 2006). The presence of phenols in the ecosystem could be ascribed to the production and degradation of numerous pesticides and the generation of industrial and municipal sewages (Rozanski, 1998; Michalowicz and Duda, 2007), while some phenols are formed during natural processes.

Phenol is present in plant and animal organic wastes as a result of decomposition (Laine and Jorgensen, 1996). Phenols formed as a result of natural processes during the composition of organic matter or synthesis of chlorinated phenols by fungi and plants have been reported (Swarts et al., 1998). Phenol is an important industrial chemical and enters the environment in air emissions and wastewater connected with its use, disinfectant and antiseptic (United States National Library of Medicine, 1987). Phenol poisoning can occur in humans after skin absorption, inhalation of vapours or through ingestion (IARC, 1989).

Phenol is capable of inducing fluorescence from 2, 7-dichlorofluorescein in HL60 human leukemia cells *in vitro* at concentrations that are not cytotoxic; which is a function of generation of reactive oxygen species (Shen et al., 1996). Kobayashi et al. (1979) report that phenol is not known to bioconcentrate significantly in aquatic organisms and states that log bioconcentration factors (BCF) in fish for phenol include 0.28 for goldfish while Freitag et al. (1984) report 1.3 for golden Orfe. Chlorophenols are the most common and the largest group of phenols and are formed in the environment by chlorination of mono and polyaromatic compounds present in soil and water. The research conducted by Michalowicz and Duda (2004) revealed that phenols are present in rivers. Phenol and phenolic substances that are usually found in the environment have been found in surface waters and surrounding air that were contaminated as a result of its release from industries and commercial products that contain phenols (Akintade et al., 2012). The research carried out by Nubi and Ajuonu (2011) reiterates that surface water and groundwater sources in Nigeria have been grossly contaminated by toxic biodegradable organic compounds and hazardous substances.

The carcinogenicity of phenols has been reported in many research publications. For example, the toxicity of phenol is noticeable due to irritation of the skin, causes necrosis; kidneys, liver, muscle and eyes damage (Clayton and Clayton, 1994) and death as a result of persistent exposure. An acute poisoning with phenol is characterised by dryness of the throat and mouth, dark urine and strong irritation of mucus membranes (Michalowicz and Duda, 2004) as chronic administration of phenol to animals leads to pathological changes in skin, lungs, liver, kidneys and urogenital tract. IARC (1972) investigate the exposure of workers to phenol vapours which caused anorexia, loss of body weight, body fatigue, muscle pain and headache. The research carried out by Paintner and Howard (1982) revealed the mutagenic activity of phenol; and that it also inhibits the synthesis and replication of DNA in HeLa cells. Medical data arising from occupational exposure reveals that patients exposed to chlorophenols fall ill of tumors, sarcoma and lung cancer (Michalowicz and Duda, 2004) while the mixture of chlorophenols or sodium salts of this compound is also carcinogenic to animals (Schweigert et al., 2001).

The United States environmental protection agency (USEPA) and WHO classifies this toxic compound as potentially carcinogenic (Schweigert et al., 2001). The cancer development in the patients exposed to phenols is related to the activation of cytochrome P450 (Michalowicz and Duda, 2004), and it has been revealed that phenols also affects the functioning of the hormonal system. Many researchers have proposed a number of methods for screening the level of ecological risk assessment techniques. For example, Zhong et al. (2010) established a mass spectrum scale using Retention Time Locking (RTL) technique and Deconvolution Reporting Software (DRS).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area is located North-east of Ibadan in South-western part of Nigeria. The topographical map of Ibadan (sheet 261 N.E.) on a scale of 1:25,000 was utilised as base map. A mobile Global Positioning System (GPS) was used to determine the coordinates of the area which lies within Longitude 3°56'E and 3°59'E, and Latitude 7°23'N and 7°25'N as shown in Fig.1. River Isebo drains South-easterly while the drainage system of the area is sub-dendritic to dendritic.

FIGURE 1: LOCATION AND DRAINAGE MAP OF THE STUDY AREA SHOWING SAMPLE POINTS

A reconnaissance survey of the study area was conducted prior to sampling. The river channel and the drainage system were mapped out for sampling in which 12 water samples were collected upstream and downstream of the watercourse respectively in a systematic manner in order to obtain representative samples. Another 8-wastewater samples were obtained randomly from the drains of the manufacturing companies, such as, pharmaceutical, confectionery, vegetable oil, bottling and dye producing outlets respectively. The wastewater samples were collected into sterile 250 ml PyrexR bottles at the point where the effluents were being discharged by the companies into the environment and then stored in a refrigerator at 2 - 8°C before conveyance to the laboratory for chemical analysis. The wastewater samples were collected at peak production periods and were denoted with WW1 to WW8 while water samples were denoted with RW1 to RW12 respectively. Samples RW1 to RW6 and RW7 to RW12 were collected upstream and downstream respectively.

Skalar Auto-Analyser (SAA) method was used for the chemical analysis of water and wastewater samples while the physico-chemical parameters were determined *in situ* using a Symphony SP80PC portable instrument to measure temperature, EC, TDS and pH respectively. The Skalar Auto-Analyser analytical procedures have been described by Thompson and Welsh (1989). The Symphony SP80PC portable instrument has the following accuracy: 1% for EC, ± 0.1 °C for temperature and ± 0.05 for pH.

RESULTS

The results obtained from chemical and statistical regression analyses of water and wastewater samples are reported in Tables 1 to 4 and represented graphically in Figs. 2 to 5 respectively.

Table 1: Concentration of phenols in wastewater samples (mg/L)

WW 1	WW 2	WW 3	WW 4	WW 5	WW 6	WW 7	WW 8
2.55	5.82	10.12	14.15	8.57	6.15	4.51	7.66

The concentration of phenols obtained for the twelve water samples are shown in Table 2 and Fig. 3 below.

Table 2: Concentration of phenols in water samples (mg/L)

RW1	RW2	RW3	RW4	RW5	RW6	RW7	RW8	RW9	RW10	RW11	RW12
2.11	1.15	1.17	1.11	0.84	0.77	0.44	0.32	0.24	0.26	0.11	0.05

Table 3 and Fig. 4 shows the value of physico-chemical parameters and linear regression of the eight wastewater samples that were analysed.

Table 3: Physico-chemical parameters of wastewater samples

Sample	EC ($\mu\text{hos/cm}$)	TDS (mg/L)	Temp ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	pH
WW1	770.6	703.4	28	6.8
WW2	1400.9	1282.6	29	6.0
WW3	2421.8	2321.7	32	5.8
WW4	2544.7	2453.9	36	5.6
WW5	1876.2	1654.8	30	5.9
WW6	1450.9	1200.1	31	5.3
WW7	850.8	799.8	27	6.1
WW8	1800.6	1522.4	30	5.4

Table 4 and Fig. 5 shows the value of physico-chemical parameters and linear regression of the twelve water samples that were analysed.

Table 4: Physico-chemical parameters of water samples

Sample	EC ($\mu\text{hos/cm}$)	TDS (mg/L)	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	pH
RW1	1000.2	985.5	22	6.0
RW2	990.4	960.5	20	6.0
RW3	995.6	965.1	20	6.5
RW4	880.2	850.5	18	6.7
RW5	820.7	800.4	18	6.7
RW6	810.1	790.9	15	6.8
RW7	622.4	615.3	15	6.8
RW8	619.8	600.3	13	6.9
RW9	540.4	518.9	13	6.9
RW10	500.1	489.2	10	7.1
RW11	482.5	466.6	10	6.9
RW12	477.7	455.8	9	6.9

DISCUSSION

The concentrations of phenol revealed a significant variability across the geographic spread of the sample points in the study area. The concentrations of phenol in wastewaters samples range from 2.55 - 14.15mg/L as shown in Table 1 and depicted in Fig. 2 while a range of 0.05 – 2.11mg/L was obtained for water samples as presented in Table 2 and Fig. 3 respectively. There appears to be a corresponding hydrochemical trend between analysed wastewater and water samples which is evident in the regression plots shown in Figs. 4 and 5 respectively.

The concentrations of phenol in water samples collected from river Isebo are higher than the recommended standards. For example, the United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA) proposed that the concentration of phenols in waters (rivers, streams, lakes) should not exceed a permissible upper limit of 0.03mg/L, while the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ) proposed by the Standards Organization of Nigeria (2007) and World Health Organization (WHO, 1993; 2002; 2003) maximum permissible level is 0.001mg/L to protect human health from possible effects of exposure to phenol by drinking water, and by ingesting plants and animals that are contaminated with this substance (Agency for Toxic Substances and Diseases Registry, 1989).

The presence of phenol in water samples collected from river Isebo could be as a result of chemical composition of additives used for the processing and manufacturing of various products or as a by-product in the study area. The physico-chemical parameters of wastewater samples, such as EC, TDS, temperature and pH vary anomalously. The coefficient of determination obtained for EC and TDS in Figs. 4 and 5 is a function of very strong positive correlation that exists between the two parameters for wastewater and water samples respectively which has been reported by Uwidia and Ukulu (2013) confirming the strong positive relationship between EC and TDS of wastewater obtained from some parts of the Delta State in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Higher concentrations of phenol revealed by chemical analysis of water samples indicate indiscriminate disposal of wastewaters into the environment and the negligence of the manufacturing industries towards the duty-of-care to manage the wastewaters. This is because the chemical analyses of wastewater and water samples carried out revealed comparatively higher concentrations of phenol than the WHO guidelines values.

Precautionary principle should be applied by imploring the polluting companies to avoid the production of likely Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) and use substitutes or modified materials, products and processes to prevent the formation and release of this substance. It is also important for environmental stakeholders and manufacturing companies to have regulatory and assessment schemes for new chemicals. This is meant to inform and strengthen adequate risk management strategies, environmental reporting, environmental communication and environmental health.

A periodic water quality monitoring programme and environmental audit should be encouraged in the study area in order to uphold sustainable environmental aesthetics and production best practice with respect to

pre-treatment of wastewater before discharging it into the environment. This environmental quality control system is expedient because many people living in the area depend on this river for domestic use.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank the officials of the companies where the wastewaters were sampled for granting the permission to carry out the exercise. The Isebo community leaders are also appreciated.

REFERENCES

- Adoni AD (1975). Studies on Microbiology of Sagar Lake. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Sagar University, Sagar, 155p.
- Agency for Toxic Substances and Diseases Registry (1989). Toxicological Profile for Phenol. [www://.eco.usa.net](http://www.eco.usa.net).
- Akintade OO, Eletta OAA and Odebunmi EO (2012). Analysis of Nitrates, Nitrites and Phenols in Surface Waters of Ilorin Environs. *Journal of Scientific Research & Reviews*, 1 (3): 033-039.
- Ayeni O (2005). Hydrogeochemical Appraisal of Effluents and Stream Quality in Parts of South-western Nigeria. Unpublished M. Sc Thesis, University of Ibadan, 85p.
- Bobranski B (1973). *Organic Chemistry*. PWN Warszawa, Poland. 420p.
- Brown VKH (1975). Decontamination Procedures for Skin Exposed to Phenolic Substances. *Arch. Environ. Health* 30: 1-10
- Clayton GD and Clayton FE (1994). *Patty's Industrial Hygiene and Toxicology*, 4th ed. John Wiley & Sons Inc. New York, Vol. 2A, 132p.
- Freitag D, Lay JP and Korte F (1984). Environmental Hazard Profile - Test Results as Related to Structures and Translation into the Environment. In: K.L.E. Kaiser (Ed.), *QSAR in Environmental Toxicology*, Proc. of the Workshop held at McMaster University, Hamilton, Ont., Aug. 16-18, 1983. D: Reidel Publ. Co., Dordrecht, Netherlands: 111-131.
- Hammer MJ (1971). *Water and Wastewater Technology*. John Wiley & Sons Inc. New York. 503p.
- IARC (1972). IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans, Vol. 47, Some Organic Solvents, Resin Monomers and Related Compounds, Pigments and Occupational Exposures in Paint Manufacture and Painting, Lyon, 287p.
- IARC (1989). Monographs on the Evaluation of the Carcinogenic Risk of Chemicals to Man. WHO International Agency for Research on Cancer. Geneva.
- Jones HA and Hockey RD (1964). The Geology of Parts of South-western Nigeria. *Geol. Survey. Nig. Bull.* 31:1-101.
- Kobayashi Y, Ichikawa T and Kobayashi H (1979). Innovation of the Caudal Neurosecretory System of the Teleost. *Gunma Symp. Endocrinol.* 16, 81-86.
- Laine M, Jorgensen K (1996). Straw Compost and Bioremediated Soil as Inocula for the Bioremediation of Chlorophenol-Contaminated Soil. *Applied Environ. Microbiol.* 54:1507-1518.
- Lewis RJ (1993). *Hawley's Condensed Chemical Dictionary*, 12th Ed., New York, Van Nostrand Reinhold, 894p.
- Michalowicz J and Duda W (2004). Chlorophenols and their Derivatives in Waters of the Drainage of the Dzierzazna River. State and Anthropogenic Changes of the Quality of Waters in Poland, Tom III ed. Burchard J. Hydrological Committee of Polish Geographical Society, University of Lodz, Lodz, 15(4):216-222.
- Michalowicz J and Duda W (2007). Phenols- Sources and Toxicity. *Polish J. of Environ. Stud.* 16 (3): 347-362.
- Mohammed Y, Aliyu AO and Audu P (2013). Concentration of Benzene and Phenol in some Petroleum based Industrial Effluents in Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Microbiology*, 2(1)007-110.
- Nubi OA and Ajuonu N (2011). Impacts of Industrial Effluent and Dumpsite Leachate Discharges on the Quality of Groundwater in Oyo state, Nigeria. *J. Biodiversity and Environ. Sci. (JBES)*. 1(3): 13-18.
- Paintner R and Howard R (1982). The HeLa DNA-Synthesis Inhibition Test as a Rapid Screen for Mutagenic Carcinogens. *Mutat. Res.* 92:427.
- Prasana KY (2001). A review of Persistent Organic Pollutants. Butterwork Publication Co. Netherlands. 220p.
- Prusse UA (2002). Phenol: Human Health Assessment Information on a Chemical Substance. EPA Article No. CASRN108-95-2. 469p
- Prusse UA and Corvalan C (2006). Preventing Diseases through Healthy Environment: Towards an Estimate of Environmental Burden of Disease. A Publication of the WHO Geneva, Switzerland.
- Rahman MA (1976). Review of Basement Complex Geology of South-western Nigeria. Elizabeth Publishing Co., Lagos, Nigeria.
- Roux PH and Althoff NF (1980). Investigation of Organic Contamination of Groundwater in South Brunswick Township, New Jersey. *J. American Water Res.* 18 (4): 144-148.
- Rozanski L (1998). The Transformation of Pesticides in Living Organisms and the Environment, Agro-Enviro Lab. Report 12.

- Schweigert N, Alexander J, Zehnder J and Eggen R (2001). Chemical Properties of Catechols and their Molecular Modes of Toxic Action in Cells from Microorganisms to Mammals. *Environ. Microbiol.* 3(81): 81-89.
- Shen Y, Shen HM, Shi CY and Ong CN (1996). Benzene Metabolites Enhanced Reactive Oxygen Species Generation in HL60 Human Leukemia Cells. *Hum. Exp. Toxic.* 15: 422-427.
- Standards Organization of Nigeria (2007). Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ). A Publication of the Nigerian Industrial Standards. http://www.unicef.org/nigeria/ng_publications/Nigerian_Standard_for_Drinking_Water_Quality.pdf
- Swarts M, Verhagen F, Field J and Wijnberg J (1998). Trichlorinated Phenols from *Hypholoma elongatum*. *Phytochem.* 49:203.
- Thompson J and Welsh AT (1989). A Validated Skalar Auto-Analyser Analytical Technique. *American J. of Analytical Chemistry.* 3:442-451.
- Thurman EM (1985). *Organic Geochemistry of Natural Waters*. Dordrecht Publishing Co. Netherlands. 220p.
- United States National Library of Medicine (1987). Hazardous Substances Data Bank (HSDB), Bethesda, MD (Record No. 113).
- Uwidia IE and Ukulu HS (2013). Studies on Electrical Conductivity and Total Dissolved Solids Concentration in Raw Domestic Wastewater Obtained From an Estate in Warri. *Greener J. Physical Sci.* 3(3):110-114.
- Wallace J (1996). Phenol. In: Kroschwitz, J.I. and Howe-Grant, M., eds., *Kirk-Othmer Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology*, 4th Ed., Vol. 18, New York, John Wiley, 602p.
- WHO (1993). *Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality*, 2nd Ed., Vol. 1, Recommendations, Geneva
- WHO (2002). *Water Pollutants: Biological Agents, Dissolved Chemicals, Non-dissolved Chemicals, Sediments, Heat*, WHO CEHA, Amman, Jordan.
- WHO (2003). *Chlorophenols in Drinking Water. Background Document for Development of WHO Guidelines for Drinking-Water Quality*. 2nd ed. Vol. 2. WHO/WSH/03.04/47.
- Zhong W, Wang D, Xu X, Luo Q, Wang B, Shan X and Wang Z (2010). Screening Level Ecological Risk Assessment for Phenols in Surface Water of the Taihu Lake. *Chemosphere*, 80 (9): 998-1005.